

A REVIEW ON THE PROGRESS AND IMPROVEMENTS IN THE SOLAR AIR HEATER TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Energy demand is rising day by day due to high growth in population and ever-increasing ostentatious needs. Conventional sources of energy are exhaustible and emissions are harmful for the environment and mankind. Solar energy as the alternative source of energy is the best solution to tackle this issue. The most effective way to convert and recover solar energy is to employ solar air/water heating equipment. The utilization of solar energy for heating purposes with a solar air heater is a great method as it requires air which is freely available and have various advantages associated with it. Solar air heaters are non-focussing type of flat plate solar collectors and have low operating temperature range that is sufficient for domestic uses as well as for few industrial applications. Various factors affect the thermal efficiency of solar air heater including low thermal conductivity and formation of laminar sub layer underneath the absorber plate. Numerous methods are employed to increase the rate of heat transfer between absorbing surface and air. The artificial roughness is reported as one of the most important and effective technique to enhance the coefficient of heat transfer. The present work represents a review of the literature that covers the basic fundamentals of solar air heater and recent developments in solar air heater technology. Various methods and geometries of artificial roughness investigated by numerous researchers are also reported in the present paper.

Keywords: Solar Energy, Solar Air Heater, Fundamentals, Artificial Roughness

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1. INTRODUCTION

Energy is a basic need for life and has become extremely important to the growth of the world's economy. Traditionally, the sources of energy have been large hydropower plants, fossil fuels, coal and wood products like gas and oil. The current oil crisis spurred conjecture over long-term changes in the global economic structure toward renewable energy sources and environmental concerns. The current energy paradigm is based on conventional energy sources, even though many developing countries find them to be unreliable and uncontrollable from a business standpoint. Number of issues including the scarcity of nuclear energy and coal deposits and the risk of pollution that endangers wildlife and flora, discourage the expansion of conventional fuels as a source of energy. Thus, it becomes evident use energy supplies that are abundant in nature and produce less or no pollution to meet energy demands. The solar energy is the source of energy from sun and most easily available on earth, it can provide for all the world's present and future energy requirements.

Numerous thermal energy applications, including drying, water and air heating, building heating and cooling, can all be directly powered by solar energy. There are several systems available for capturing solar energy, including helio-thermal, helio-electrical, and helio-chemical technologies [1]. Utilizing solar collectors to heat the fluid for various uses is known as helio-thermal energy use. Solar collectors are broadly classified into two categories that is flat plate solar collectors and concentrated solar collectors. Temperature range is low in the former and high in the later one. Solar water heater and solar air heater are two flat plate collectors for heating water and air respectively for further using it for various applications. Solar air heaters are preferred over solar water heaters as they are free from corrosion and freezing issues. Moreover, solar air heaters can be fabricated by using cheap and easily available material.

Fig. 1. Classification of Solar Energy Technology [1].

2. MECHANISM OF SOLAR AIR HEATER:

Solar air heater is a solar flat plate collector that utilizes sunlight to heat air and widely employed for solar energy heating applications. The absorber plate, which is a black-painted flat surface with substantial absorption of incoming radiation, clear glass covering and air as a fluid flow make up the solar air heater. A conventional solar air heater is shown in the Fig. 2 [2]. The basic mechanism of a solar air heater involves the following components and processes:

- (a) Collector: The solar air heater typically consists of a collector, which is exposed to sunlight. The collector is designed to absorb solar radiation efficiently. It is often made of materials with high thermal conductivity and is coated with a dark, absorbing surface to maximize sunlight absorption.
- (b) Absorption of Solar Radiation: When sunlight strikes the collector, the dark surface absorbs a significant portion of the solar radiation. The absorbed energy is then converted into heat, raising the temperature of the collector.
- (c) Heat Transfer to Air: Air is drawn into the collector through an inlet. As the air passes over the heated collector surface, it gains thermal energy through conduction and radiation.
- (d) Flow Path: The design of the solar air heater includes a specific flow path for the air to ensure efficient heat transfer. The air flow may be driven by natural convection (buoyancy) or with the help of a fan for forced convection.
- (e) Ducting System: The heated air is then directed through a ducting system to the desired application, such as a living space or a drying chamber.
- (f) Temperature Control (Optional): In some solar air heaters, temperature control mechanisms such as dampers or valves may be incorporated to regulate the flow of air and maintain the desired temperature.
- (g) Outlet: The heated air is released through an outlet into the space where it is needed.
- (f) Backflow Prevention (Optional): Some systems may include mechanisms to prevent backflow of air during periods of low or no sunlight to avoid heat loss.

Fig. 2. Typical Solar Air Heater [2].

3. FACTORS AFFECTING EFFICIENCY OF SOLAR AIR HEATER

Although, solar air heaters have an advantage of being corrosion and freezing resistant, the lower specific heat and air density result in significant pressure losses which ultimately requires high flow rates. The thermal conductivity of air is also low due to which leads to decrease in heat transfer. Another reason of solar air heater's less thermal efficiency is the development of laminar sub layer underneath the absorbing plate which reduces the rate of heater transfer between the surface and air. Multiple methods are suggested by various investigators to enhance the thermal efficiency of solar heater such as making air to pass through multiple passages, reducing the thermal losses, enhancing the solar irradiation on to the solar air heater etc. However, increasing the heat transfer coefficient by incorporating artificial roughness is considered as the best method as it increases heat transfer rate by inducing turbulence in the laminar zone with some friction loss. Many researchers have reported different types and geometries of artificial roughness to increase the heat augmentation of the solar air heater with minimum friction penalty. Heat transfer is evaluated in the non-dimensional form as Nusselt Number and Friction loss is evaluated in the non-dimensional form as reported by Bhushan and Singh [3].

$$\text{Nusselt Number (Nu)} = \frac{hL}{K}$$

$$\text{Friction Factor (f)} = \frac{\Delta PD}{2LV^2\rho}$$

Biondi et al. [4] explained how the performances of conventional solar air heaters could be based on two parameters namely specific air flow rate (G) and geometric coefficient (K) by assuming fully developed turbulent flow, rectangular ducts, and identical conditions regarding construction typology, environmental parameters, material choice, and inlet temperature. In the hypotheses, the geometric coefficient of the collector (K) could be utilized in experimental tests to group air heaters with similar geometries. For collectors of type D, the formula published for UL (assuming equal temperatures for the air above and below the absorber) facilitated easy computation through the zero-capacitance model. The provided diagram proved useful for both comparing the performances of various collector types and selecting the construction type that best satisfied specific usage conditions.

Prasad and Saini [5] explained how the optimal thermohydraulic performance conditions in artificially roughened solar air heaters were obtained when the roughness height was slightly higher than the transition sublayer thickness. Furthermore, a relationship between roughness and flow parameters was presented in the form of design curves, which led to the selection of these parameters to achieve optimal thermohydraulic performance in artificially roughened solar air heaters. Bhargava et al. [6] combined radiative as well as convective losses due to the wind. Its value was taken as $25 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. All the other radiative heat transfer coefficients were taken as $6 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The glass transmittance z was taken as 0.9, plate absorptance α was 0.9, and glass absorptance α_g was 0.06. The solar absorptance and the radiative properties of the solar cell surface were assumed to be the same as those of the black absorber plate ($\alpha\eta = \alpha\rho$). The back loss coefficient U_B was $0.692 \text{ W/m}^2 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The forced convective heat transfer coefficients h_1 and h_2 were calculated from the relation. Mohammad et al. [7] identified the drawbacks of conventional solar air heaters which were heat loss to the ambient through the glass cover and poor heat convection from the absorber to the airstream. Then, the performance of a counter-flow solar air heater with a porous matrix was analyzed and the results were compared with conventional solar air heaters. Under normal operating conditions, the analysis indicated that the suggested heater thermal efficiency could exceed 75%. The efficiency of this type of collector was much higher than the efficiency of conventional air heaters. The collector minimized heat loss to the ambient and maximized heat transfer to the airstream. The construction cost of the counter-flow heater was comparable with the construction cost of the double-glazing heater. However, the pressure drop (pumping power) was higher for the suggested heater, but this factor was not so significant for low flow rates.

Fig. 3. Effect of height of roughness element [5].

4. LATEST APPROACH OF ARTIFICIAL ROUGHNESS AND ITS GEOMETRIES

Abbasov et al. [8] conducted the study to show the possibility of using a solar drying installation to save thermal or electric energy spent on drying transformer windings. The efficiency of the collector and the solar dryer could be improved by using metal shavings with a diameter of 0.01 meters, placed 0.3 meters apart from each other and attached to the walls of a smooth blackened metal sheet along the main direction of the airflow. Rajendran et al. [9] compared the performance of a conventional solar air heater experimentally to a modified solar air heater with multi-geometry baffles over the absorber plate as shown in the Fig. 4. The effect of baffles on energy gain, top loss, and thermal efficiency was investigated by changing mass flow rates. The studies led to the following conclusions: adding multi-geometry baffles as artificial roughness over the absorber plate significantly improved the performance of a solar air heater. Thermal efficiency and energy gain was found maximum at 0.04 kg/s mass flow rate. The system performs better when the mass flow rate was raised. The average thermal efficiency of a solar air heater with a multi-geometry baffle was 40.8%, 58.2%, 68.2%, and 77.4% for the studied flow rates. That is 12.8%, 10.2%, 12.3%, and 13.5% at the same flow rates.

Fig. 4. 3D model of proposed solar air heater by Rajendran et al. [9]

Kadijani et al. [10] analyzed the heat performance of humid air flow inside a solar air heater with V-shaped ribs on absorber plate using a commercial FVM code. Unlike previous studies focusing on dry air flow, authors specifically investigated humid air flow. It was observed that increasing the relative humidity of the incoming humid air from 0% to 50% enhanced the heat transfer rate by up to 6%. Additionally, when the Reynolds number increased by 200%, the average Nusselt number for a rib spacing of 6mm increased by about 7.3%, while for a spacing of 16mm, it increased by about 31.4%. Interestingly, we found that within the range of Reynolds numbers we examined, the rib spacing did not significantly affect the pressure drop. Fig. 5. Shows average Nusselt Number and pressure drop versus Reynolds number for two different rib pitches at a relative humidity of 50%. Alsaiari et al. [11] yielded valuable insights for optimizing designs of artificial cone-shaped protrusions on absorber surfaces as shown in the Fig. 6. aiming to enhance heat flow efficiency while minimizing pumping energy requirements. Notably, increases in Reynolds number correlated with reductions in both friction factor and Nusselt number, with rough absorber plates exhibiting significantly higher values compared to smooth ones. Cone-shaped roughness configurations, particularly at a Reynolds number of 8000, demonstrated remarkable enhancements in Nusselt number, peaking at 64.5% for specific dimensions. Similarly, maximum increases in friction factor, reaching 153.3%, were observed under similar roughness conditions. Efficiency indices for cone-shaped roughness were found to peak at 0.8233, further emphasizing their potential in heat transfer enhancement. The consistency between theoretical predictions and experimental results underscored the reliability of the study's findings. Notably, predictions for average friction factor and Nusselt number closely matched actual values, indicating the effectiveness of the correlations employed in the analysis. Overall, these findings provide valuable insights for optimizing heat transfer processes in various engineering applications.

Fig. 5. Average Nusselt Number and pressure drop versus Reynolds number for two different rib pitches at a relative humidity of 50% [10].

Singh et al. [12] determined the variation of the flow and thermal characteristics in terms of nusselt number, effectiveness, exergy, second law efficiency, and friction losses for the range of Reynolds numbers 11000–15000. The absorber plate was set to a constant heat flux of 1000 W/m². The ribs of the absorber plate intensified turbulence in the flow, resulting in more mixing in the flow and increasing the heat transfer rate at the expense of pressure drop. In the case of curved solar air heater devices, centrifugal and centripetal forces provided scope for the formation of dean/secondary flow vortices which had vortex pairs of equal magnitude with opposite directions of rotation, one clockwise and the other anticlockwise. Fig. 7. Shows the geometry of a curved solar air heater having 25° curvature angle with three different shapes of ribs. The curvature type flow channel augmented the rate of heat exchange in the flow while interacting with the hot absorber plate.

Fig. 6. Schematic view of cone shaped roughness on the absorber surface [11].

Fig. 7. Geometry of a curved solar air heater having 25° curvature angle with three different shapes of ribs [12].

Saxena et al. [13] made an attempt to review of solar air heaters and mentioned that liquid collectors suffered from the possibility of water freezing as a heat transfer fluid in cold climates, fluid leakage, and corrosion. For air as a fluid, leakage, corrosion, and freezing were not major problems in solar heaters. They were simple in construction and did not need high technology for maintenance or repair. However, air as a heat transfer fluid suffered from its low heat capacity and poor heat transfer from the absorber to the flowing air. Therefore, many attempts were made to overcome this problem by using high mass flow rates and using extended surfaces to increase the heat transfer area and hence the heat transfer rate to the flowing air. Gill and Singh [14] demonstrated thermal efficiency for single glazed, double-glazed and packed bed solar air heaters.

Full and sectional view of single glazed solar air heater is shown in Fig. 8. For all flow rates, the maximum average thermal efficiency was 37.45% for single glazed and 24.07% for double glazed solar air heaters during summer, with corresponding figures for winter being 30.29% and 45.05%, respectively. For the same initial investment, low-cost solar air heaters collected more energy than packed bed solar air heaters. Specifically, for a flow rate of $0.020 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ per m^2 aperture area, the solar energy gain per unit investment was 0.13 kJ per US\$ for single glazed, 0.10 kJ per US\$ for double glazed, and 0.03 kJ per US\$ for packed bed solar air heater during summer, with corresponding figures for winter being 0.08 kJ per US\$, 0.07 kJ per US\$ and 0.02 kJ per US\$ respectively. Farmers could utilize solar air heaters for drying purposes for short periods after harvesting (1–2 months a year), and during the off-season, these lightweight low-cost solar air heaters could be conveniently stored indoors.

Fig. 8. Full and sectional view of single glazed solar air heater [14].

Chamoli et al. [15] aimed to explore the effect of various parameters on the performance of double pass solar air heaters. The mass flow rate of air and the porosity of packing material were identified as important parameters influencing the system's performance. Additionally, the recycle ratio was noted as a significant parameter affecting the performance of double pass solar air heaters with external recycling. It was observed that maximum efficiency is achieved when the channel depths and mass flow rate of air are consistent in both the upper and lower ducts. Several analytical and experimental studies were conducted with packed bed and fins integrated double pass solar air heaters, demonstrating a significant increase in performance compared to conventional systems. Aharwal et al. [16] experimentally investigated heat transfer and friction characteristics and found that providing a gap in the inclined rib resulted in a considerable enhancement in the heat transfer coefficient and friction factor of a rectangular artificially roughened duct with inclined and transverse discrete ribs on the absorber plate of a solar air heater. Compared to the smooth surface, the rib-roughened surface yielded an increase of about 2.83 and 3.60 times in the Nusselt number and friction factor, respectively, for the range of parameters investigated. The maximum heat transfer enhancement occurred at the relative gap position of 0.25 with the relative gap width of 1.0 for the relative roughness pitch of 8.0, an angle of attack of 60° , and relative roughness height of 0.037. Additionally, the maximum value of the friction factor occurred for discrete transverse ribs with a relative roughness pitch of 8.0. Correlations were developed for the Nusselt number and friction factor as a function of roughness and flow parameters, which were found to predict the Nusselt number and friction factor values within a deviation from +12% to 10% and $\pm 10\%$, respectively, for the range of Reynolds number from 3000 to 18,000, relative roughness height from 0.018 to 0.037, relative gap position from 0 to 0.67, and relative gap width from 0 to 2.0 at a relative roughness pitch of 8 and an angle of attack of 60° .

Gupta et al. [17] tried to improve the efficiency by using roughened geometries in the duct of the solar air heater. The η_{ef} -based criterion suggested using roughened geometries for very large values of Re. The η_{II} -based criterion showed that at very large values of Re, the η_{II} could be negative or the exergy of pump work required exceeded the exergy of heat energy collected by the solar air heater. Thus, η_{II} provided a meaningful criterion for performance evaluation. There was not a single roughened geometry that gave the best exergetic performance for the whole range of Re. For larger flow cross-section areas of the solar air heater duct, along with low Re, the roughened geometry should create more turbulence, while smooth surfaces, circular ribs, and V-shaped ribs were suitable for smaller flow cross-section areas of the solar air heater duct and high Re. Saxena et al. [18] made an attempt to review of solar air heaters and mentioned that liquid collectors suffered from the possibility of water freezing as a heat transfer fluid in cold climates, fluid leakage, and corrosion. For air as a fluid, leakage, corrosion, and freezing were not major problems in solar heaters. They were simple in construction and did not need high technology for maintenance or repair. However, air as a heat transfer fluid suffered from its low heat capacity and poor heat transfer from the absorber to the flowing air. Therefore, many attempts were made to overcome this problem by using high mass flow rates and using extended surfaces to increase the heat transfer area and hence the heat transfer rate to the flowing air.

5. CFD AND NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

Korpale et al. [19] installed rectangular sectioned fins on absorber surface to help in creating wall induced turbulence affecting the temperature of the air as well as the local temperature of walls in contact with hot air. The design combinations are generated using the CCD method of response surface methodology and are tested by the CFD approach. The heat transfer enhancement is characterized by enhancement in Nusselt number. Nevertheless, there was a simultaneous increase in the friction factor. Hence it is accounted by parameter THP. Applying created correlations, the highest THP attained was found as 2.77 at Re 20000, P/e as 17.22, e/D as 0.044 and w/e as 0.5. According to the model equations, a system's Nusselt number will grow steadily as Re rises, accounting for the fluid domain's maximal heat dissipation.

Karamveer et al. [20] discussed various methods to improve the performance of the basic configuration of solar air heaters. A general approach was employed involving the development of a thermo-hydraulic mathematical model for a modified solar air heater and the integration of various heat transfer and friction factor correlations from previous studies. Numerical studies were conducted to predict the thermo-hydraulic performance of roughened absorber surfaces of solar air heater, focusing on thermal and effective efficiency. Comparison was made between the thermal and effective efficiency of rough surfaces and smooth surfaces under identical experimental conditions. Certain rib geometries as shown in the Fig. 8 such as broken-arc shaped ribs combined with staggered-arc rib pieces, exhibited superior performance. Thermal and effective efficiency were found to be strongly influenced by roughness parameters such as Re and $\Delta T/I$. Optimal performance was typically achieved under specific parameter combinations. Moreover, certain roughness configurations consistently demonstrated higher thermal and effective efficiency compared to others, especially with increasing values of $\Delta T/I$. Matheswaran et al. [21] investigated the influence of mass flow rate, jet diameter ratio, stream wise pitch ratio, and span wise pitch ratio on the energetic efficiency of a single-pass double-duct jet plate solar air heater. Based on the simulation results, the maximum effective and energetic efficiency for single pass double SPDDJPSAH reached 72.3% and 4.36% respectively at a stream wise pitch ratio of $(X/Dh) = 1.739$, span wise pitch ratio of $(Y/Dh) = 0.869$, and jet diameter ratio of $(Dj/Dh) = 0.065$ marking a 21.2% and 22.4% increase compared to a single-pass single-duct jet plate solar air heater. The optimized values for jet plate design parameters were $X/Dh = 1.739$, $Y/Dh = 0.869$, and $Dj/Dh = 0.065$, maximizing the energy efficiency while suggesting the temperature rise parameter ($\Delta T/I$) for the design of SPDDJPSAH. The maximum energy efficiency was achieved at a mass flow rate of 0.0035 kg/s.

Furthermore, an increase in mass flow rate led to increased energy destruction due to friction and decreased energy efficiency. In laminar flow conditions, enhancing the stream and span wise pitch ratio improved energy efficiency by reducing interference between the jets, while in turbulent conditions, lower values of X/D_h & Y/D_h were preferred due to higher ratios of total jet area to heat transfer area.

Fig. 9. Calculation procedure followed by Korpale et al. [19].

Yadav et al. [22] presented a detailed review of the literature concerning the application of Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) in the design of solar air heaters. Additionally, a CFD investigation was carried out to select the best turbulence model for the design of a solar air heater. Various Reynolds numbers ranging from 2000 to 20000 were analysed and friction factors were recorded for each using different turbulence models such as Standard k-epsilon, RNG k-epsilon, Realizable k-epsilon, Standard k-omega, and SST k-omega. The variation of friction factor with Reynolds number was illustrated in the figure provided. The study utilized the CFD code ANSYS FLUENT v12.1 to simulate fluid flow through a conventional solar air heater, considering a two-dimensional flow. Simulation of solar air heater at different flow rate is shown in Fig. 10. The influence of the five different turbulence models on the quality of the obtained results was examined. Priyam et al. [23] explained how the development of mathematical models provided reasonable predictions of the performance of both plate and wavy fin solar air heaters as seen in Fig. 11. Secondly, analytical equations yielded values for the total loss coefficient, collector efficiency factor, collector heat removal factor, temperature rise, thermal efficiency, pressure drop, and thermohydraulic efficiency for wavy fin solar air heaters. Thirdly, various performance parameters of wavy finned solar air heaters were compared to those of plane solar air heaters. Fourthly, increasing the air flow rate through the solar air heater resulted in higher collector efficiency but also increased pressure drop. Fifthly, the use of wavy fins increased the heat transfer surface area and heat transfer coefficient, thereby improving the thermal performance of the solar air heater. Sixthly, it was found that wavy fin absorber solar air heaters exhibited higher thermal efficiency and effective temperature rise compared to corresponding flat plate collectors operating under similar conditions, with percentage enhancements ranging from 62.53% to 29.39% and 63.41% to 29.43% at mass flow rates of 0.0138 kg/s and 0.0834 kg/s with the least fin spacing. Lastly, the maximum enhancement in thermohydraulic efficiency was found with wavy fin solar air heaters having the least fin spacing, showing enhancements of 35.83% and 17.56% at mass flow rates of 0.0138 kg/s and 0.0834 kg/s respectively, compared to plane solar air heaters.

Layek et al. [24] presented a mathematical model for predicting the entropy generation of a solar air heater with a chamfered rib-groove roughened absorber plate as shown in Fig. 12. The effect of the roughness parameter on entropy generation was examined. It was observed that entropy generation decreased as the relative roughness height increased. The combination of a relative roughness pitch of 6, relative groove position of 0.4, and chamfer angle of 181 exhibited the least increase in entropy generation.

Fig. 10. Simulation of solar air heater at different flow rate [22].

Fig. 11. Solar air heater with wavy finned absorber [23].

Kulkarni and Kim [25] investigated the best form for obstructions linked to a solar air heater using three-dimensional Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes calculations of fluid flow and heat transmission. Based on the hydraulic diameter of the channel, the Reynolds number was between 6800 and 10,000. The thermal and aerodynamic characteristics of the solar air heater are measured using the Nusselt number and friction factor, respectively. Three obstacle configurations and four distinct obstacle shapes; rectangular, trapezoidal, pentagonal, and U-shaped were examined to see how they affected the solar air heater's effectiveness. The pentagonal barrier shape shown the maximum performance independent of the Reynolds number and the findings demonstrate that the performance factor (defined as a ratio of thermal to aerodynamic performance) was above unity for all examined scenarios.

Fig. 12. Solar air heater with a chamfered rib-groove roughened absorber plate [24].

6. CONCLUSION

With the increasing demand for energy-efficient and eco-friendly heating systems, solar air heaters have gained significant attention in recent years. The solar air heater captures sunlight, absorbs its energy and transfers this energy to air, which is then used for space heating, drying and many other purposes. The present review paper on solar air heater provides a basic understanding of solar air heater and analysis of the current state of the solar air heating technology. The efficiency of a solar air heater depends on factors such as the design of the collector, the absorber material, its roughness configuration, and the air flow characteristics. It is observed from the literature review that creating artificial roughness on the absorbing material by opting different methods and shapes gives fruitful results. Key findings revealed that the shape, size, and arrangement of artificial roughness on the duct surface are crucial for optimizing solar air heater performance. The paper also presents various simulation models and experimental studies that have been conducted to evaluate the performance of solar air heaters under different operating conditions. However, limited research has been conducted on corrugated/conical shaped absorber surfaces and there have been no reported studies on artificially roughened double pass solar air heaters to compare heat transfer characteristics and friction factors with conventional systems.

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